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PI3K subunit composition in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer.

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Regulation of energy in the cell, signaling in the mTOR, AKT and PI3K pathways, influences physiologically relevant outcomes in cancer involving interactions with the immune system or that influence disease progression in cancer. We used whole transcriptome technologies to systematically define requirements for metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with a common solid tumor type, cancer of the breast (breast cancer). Among the genes regulating “regional” metastatic disease progression through PI3K pathway signaling control were PIK3R5, PIK3R4 and VAC14.